

The Power-Vacuum Paradox: Middle-Power Projection and Structural Vulnerability in Turkey's Somalia Engagement

Giacomo Cavalcabò

Università di Firenze / Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa

Preprint
February 2026

Corresponding author: giacomo.cavalcabo@edu.unifi.it

This paper is written in a personal capacity. The views expressed do not necessarily represent the positions of the author's academic institutions.

Abstract. Turkey faces a structural paradox in Somalia: the conditions for sustained success remain largely outside Ankara's control, yet its deepening commitment generates dependencies that make disengagement increasingly costly. This paper analyses the February 2024 Defence and Economic Cooperation Framework Agreement within the broader framework of Turkey's composite power projection in Somalia, drawing on neoclassical realist theory (Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell, 2016) and pre-mortem analysis as a structured analytic technique. It identifies three interconnected vulnerability pathways – local fragility (clan dynamics, Al-Shabaab, humanitarian crises), regional competition (Ethiopia-Somaliland tensions, Gulf rivalries, AUSSOM's funding crisis) and global shifts (Houthi disruption, US retrenchment, great-power competition) – and shows how domestic intervening variables (Erdoğan's leader images, neo-Ottomanist strategic culture, hyper-presidential institutions) systematically bias Turkish foreign policy toward escalation even when systemic conditions counsel restraint. We term this dynamic the *power-vacuum paradox* and develop three failure scenarios that illustrate its operational implications.

1 Introduction: a new phase in Turkey-Somalia relations

On 8 February 2024, Turkey and Somalia signed a Defence and Economic Cooperation Framework Agreement that represents a watershed moment in the bilateral relationship. The agreement commits the Turkish Navy to patrolling Somalia’s territorial waters for a period of ten years, grants Turkey 30% of revenues from maritime resources discovered in the Somali exclusive economic zone and establishes a comprehensive programme for training and equipping Somali naval forces.¹

This accord marks a qualitative transformation in Turkey’s engagement with Somalia. Since the landmark visit of President Erdoğan to Mogadishu in 2011 – the first by a non-African head of state since 1993 – Ankara has built an extensive presence in the country encompassing humanitarian aid, military training (Camp Turksom, operational since 2017), economic investment, educational programmes and diplomatic mediation (Ozkan and Orakci, 2015; Wasuge, 2016). The 2024 agreement, however, shifts the relationship from an asymmetric donor-recipient model to a structured partnership with mutual economic obligations and binding security commitments.

The timing of the agreement is far from coincidental. It comes amid a convergence of destabilising developments: the Ethiopian-Somaliland Memorandum of Understanding (January 2024) that threatened Somalia’s territorial integrity; the Houthi attacks on Red Sea shipping (from late 2023) that elevated the strategic importance of the Gulf of Aden; and the uncertain transition from the African Union Transition Mission in Somalia (ATMIS) to its successor, AUSSOM.²

This paper analyses the strategic implications of Turkey’s deepening maritime and security engagement in Somalia. It addresses the following research question: *Under what conditions is Turkey’s composite engagement in Somalia most vulnerable to failure*

¹The agreement was signed on 8 February 2024 at Ankara by Defence Ministers Yaşar Güler and Abdulkadir Mohamed Nur, ratified by the Somali parliament on 21 February (213 votes in favour, 3 against). The full text has not been publicly released; the terms reported here are based on official statements and authoritative reporting. See: “Turkey and Somalia sign defence and economic cooperation deal,” *Al Jazeera*, 22 February 2024; “Turkey, Somalia sign maritime defence deal,” *Reuters*, 8 February 2024; Soufan Center analysis, 29 February 2024. The agreement covers joint air, land and naval operations, anti-piracy, counter-terrorism, combating IUU fishing and development of port and naval infrastructure. A follow-on hydrocarbon agreement (March 2024) authorises Turkish Petroleum Corporation to explore up to 15,000 km² of Somali offshore and onshore territory under terms that have drawn criticism for their asymmetry (Nordic Monitor, April 2025).

²ATMIS’s mandate expired on 31 December 2024. The UN Security Council authorised its successor, the African Union Support and Stabilization Mission in Somalia (AUSSOM), through Resolution 2767 (2024). AUSSOM became operational on 1 January 2025 with an authorised strength of approximately 12,626 troops – a significant reduction from ATMIS’s peak of 19,000. The mission’s composition has been politically contentious: Somalia requested the exclusion of Ethiopian troops (in retaliation for the Somaliland MoU), while Egypt secured the inclusion of its forces for the first time.

and how do local, regional and global risk factors interact to amplify or mitigate this vulnerability?

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 reviews the existing literature on Turkey-Somalia relations and positions this paper’s contribution relative to the descriptive and theoretical literatures. Section 3 outlines the theoretical framework (neoclassical realism) and the analytical method (pre-mortem analysis as a structured analytic technique). Section 4 provides a compressed empirical overview of Turkey’s composite engagement. Section 5 applies the pre-mortem analysis across local, regional and global levels and operationalises the neoclassical realist framework through its domestic intervening variables. Section 6 discusses risk interactions, develops the power-vacuum paradox, constructs three failure scenarios, situates Turkey’s predicament within a comparative perspective on middle powers in fragile states and formalises the paradox with scope conditions. Section 7 concludes with theoretical implications and policy relevance.

2 Turkey in Somalia: literature, gaps and the contribution of this paper

The scholarly literature on Turkey’s engagement in the Horn of Africa has grown substantially since Erdoan’s 2011 Mogadishu visit transformed a bilateral relationship of marginal strategic significance into a widely discussed case of emerging-power activism. Yet it has developed unevenly, producing a rich empirical record alongside a relatively thin analytical architecture – a gap this paper seeks to address.

2.1 The descriptive literature on Turkey-Somalia relations

The foundational contributions are primarily descriptive and broadly positive in their assessment of Turkey’s model. Cannon (2016) provided the first systematic account of Turkey’s Somalia engagement, situating it within Ankara’s broader Africa strategy and documenting the multi-agency architecture through which the AKP government converted humanitarian impulse into sustained political presence. Wasuge (2016) and Sucuoglu and Stearns (2016) complemented this from a Somali perspective, arguing that Turkey’s unconditional aid model resonated with Somali actors precisely because it departed from Western conditionality regimes – a finding subsequently confirmed at the aggregate level by Hackenesch, Leininger and Mross (2020) in their comparative analysis of European and non-Western development donors. Ozkan and Orakci (2015) situated Turkey’s Africa engagement within its broader foreign policy shift under the AKP, interpreting Mogadishu as a laboratory for the “Ankara Consensus” – a mode of South-South partnership combining

aid, investment and Islamic soft power without governance conditionality.

Donelli (2021) offers the most theoretically ambitious treatment of the period to 2020. His monograph argues that Turkey’s Africa strategy constitutes a distinctive “multi-agency model” in which state institutions, semi-public bodies and nominally independent NGOs operate as coordinated instruments of state-directed soft power, thereby blurring the boundary between humanitarian action and strategic projection in ways that are difficult for competitors to replicate. Van den Berg and Meester (2019) extended this analysis to the regional level, tracing how Turkey’s bilateralism interacted with Gulf rivalries to produce a competitive dynamic that the authors read, on balance, as stabilising for Somalia’s fragile central government. Cannon and Donelli (2020) advanced the most systematic regional framing, deploying Regional Security Complex Theory to show how the Horn of Africa and Middle East security complexes have become structurally interdependent – a framework within which Turkey functions as a “penetrating power” with interests that straddle both complexes.

The literature’s common limitation is temporal and analytical. Produced largely before 2022 and drawing on the 2011–2020 period, it evaluates an engagement that was still predominantly discretionary: Turkey could modulate its presence, redirect resources and reframe its role without incurring material costs beyond reputational ones. The 2024 Defence and Economic Cooperation Framework Agreement and the subsequent hydrocarbon deal represent a qualitative discontinuity that the existing literature, by definition, has not confronted. When commitments become contractual, when naval assets are deployed and when revenue-sharing clauses extend over decades, the risk calculus changes in ways that a predominantly descriptive literature is ill-equipped to capture.

2.2 Neoclassical realism and middle-power projection

The theoretical literature offers complementary resources. Neoclassical realism has been applied to Turkish foreign policy with increasing frequency, though rarely to the Africa theatre specifically. Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell (2016) provide the most rigorous contemporary statement of the framework, formalising the concept of the “imperfect transmission belt” through which systemic pressures are filtered by domestic intervening variables before they produce foreign policy outcomes. Previous applications to Turkey have focused primarily on the European and Middle Eastern theatres: Uzun (2021) traces how domestic political consolidation under the AKP reconfigured Turkey’s threat perceptions and strategic ambitions, while Öni and Kutlay (2020), in their analysis of Turkey’s structural position within the global core–periphery divide, show that AKP foreign policy expansion across multiple theatres reflects a political economy logic in which external activism compensates for domestic structural vulnerabilities – a pattern whose implica-

tions for the sustainability of overseas commitments the present paper takes as a central concern.

The middle-power literature offers a further framing. Jordaan (2003) and Nolte (2010) distinguish between traditional middle powers – established states with stable extractive capacity and consolidated domestic institutions – and emerging middle powers whose regional ambitions structurally precede the economic base required to sustain them. Turkey belongs clearly to the latter category; what the literature has not yet done is connect this structural position to the specific vulnerability patterns that emerge when emerging middle powers engage in fragile states under permissive systemic conditions. This is the gap the present paper addresses.

2.3 Positioning this paper

This paper makes three contributions to the existing literature. First, it provides an explicit operationalisation of neoclassical realist theory applied to Turkey’s Horn of Africa engagement, explaining *why* Ankara persists despite deteriorating domestic conditions rather than merely documenting *that* it does. Second, it introduces the pre-mortem as a structured analytic method for identifying failure pathways and their cross-level interactions – an approach absent from the largely descriptive Turkey-Somalia literature and better suited to forward-looking policy analysis than retrospective case study. Third, it proposes the concept of the *power-vacuum paradox* as a mid-range theoretical contribution: a framework for understanding the specific vulnerability of emerging middle-power projection in fragile states that, as the comparison with France in the Sahel suggests, may have applicability beyond the Turkish case.

The paper does not dispute the achievements documented in the existing literature. Turkey’s engagement model has delivered tangible benefits to Somalia and constitutes a genuine innovation in South-South development cooperation. What the 2024 agreement changes – and what the existing literature has not yet had occasion to address – is the cost structure of disengagement. This paper analyses the conditions under which that cost structure could become decisive.

3 Theoretical framework and analytical method

3.1 Neoclassical realism and middle-power projection

The analytical challenge posed by Turkey’s Somalia engagement is, at root, a puzzle about misalignment: why would a middle power facing severe macroeconomic strain invest so heavily in a theatre that sits well outside its immediate security perimeter? Structural

realism alone cannot answer this, because the systemic distribution of power creates permissive conditions for Turkish projection in the Horn without actually compelling it. Nor can a purely domestic-politics account suffice, since the timing and escalation pattern of Ankara’s commitments track closely with shifts in the regional security environment – the Ethiopian-Somaliland crisis, Houthi disruption, AUSSOM’s uncertain transition – that no amount of ideological motivation would have produced on its own.

Neoclassical realism, as reformulated by Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell (2016), offers a way through this impasse precisely because it refuses to privilege either level of explanation. The framework treats systemic pressures – the distribution of power alongside threat perceptions and the strategic opportunities that arise when great-power attention migrates elsewhere – as setting the broad parameters within which states operate, while insisting that the *specific* policy response depends on how those pressures are filtered through what Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell term the “imperfect transmission belt” of domestic politics. Previous applications of neoclassical realism to Turkish foreign policy have concentrated on the European and Middle Eastern theatres (Uzun, 2021), with domestic political consolidation under the AKP identified as the primary driver of expanded strategic ambition; the present paper extends this analytical tradition to the Horn of Africa, a theatre where, as Section 2 notes, the systemic opportunity structure and the domestic transmission belt have interacted with particular intensity since 2011. The intervening variables that constitute this belt – leader images, strategic culture, state-society relations, domestic institutional constraints – do not merely transmit systemic signals; they refract them, sometimes amplifying and sometimes dampening the impulse toward action abroad.

Applied to the Turkish case, the framework illuminates what a single-level analysis would miss. The power vacuum that opened across the Horn of Africa as US engagement waned, as Somalia fragmented and as Gulf rivalries intensified did create a *permissive environment* for projection – yet the particular form that projection assumed, humanitarian-first and Islam-compatible, bilateral rather than multilateral, channelled through agencies like TİKA and Diyanet rather than through international organisations, was decisively shaped by the AKP’s neo-Ottomanist ideology, by the “Strategic Depth” doctrine that Davutoğlu (2001) articulated and by the domestic political utility of an activist foreign policy that could demonstrate Turkey’s emergence as what Davutoğlu called a *merkez ülke* (Cannon, 2016; Van den Berg and Meester, 2019). Stripping away the domestic variables would leave us with a permissive environment explanation that could account for *some* middle power stepping into the Horn – but not for why Turkey did so, in the way it did and with the escalatory trajectory that has culminated in the 2024 defence agreement.

The framework also generates a testable expectation that structures the rest of this

paper. If power projection abroad depends on the sustained alignment between systemic opportunity and domestic extractive capacity, then that projection becomes vulnerable the moment either condition deteriorates – when the external environment grows more competitive because new actors enter or alliances shift or when internal capacity contracts under the weight of economic crisis and eroding public consent. The pre-mortem analysis in Section 5 is built on precisely this logic, tracing the conditions under which the alignment that has sustained Turkey’s engagement might break down.

3.2 Pre-mortem analysis as a Structured Analytic Technique

Gary Klein formalised the pre-mortem in the early 2000s (published as Klein, 2007) as a deceptively simple intervention against overconfidence in project planning: rather than asking whether a venture will succeed, the analyst assumes it has already failed and works backward to identify the causes. The US Intelligence Community subsequently adopted the technique as a Structured Analytic Technique for challenging assumptions and surfacing failure pathways that conventional forecasting tends to suppress, a lineage traced in detail by Pherson and Heuer (2020).

What makes the pre-mortem analytically powerful is the cognitive reorientation it forces. The prompt for this paper – “*Assume that within the medium term, Turkey’s composite engagement in Somalia has failed to achieve its strategic objectives; what factors, individually or in combination, caused this failure?*” – compels attention to disconfirming evidence that an optimistic baseline would screen out. Confirmation bias loses its grip when the analyst begins from the outcome rather than from the status quo and the planning fallacy recedes once obstacles must be catalogued systematically rather than weighed against a presumed trajectory of success (Klein, 2007; Comiskey and Larrañaga, 2019).

The pre-mortem applied here is organised along the three classical levels of analysis that Waltz (1959) identified – local dynamics within Somalia itself, regional competition across the Horn of Africa and the Gulf, global systemic shifts driven by great-power repositioning – while a fourth, domestic, layer operationalises the neoclassical realist intervening variables that mediate between external pressures and Ankara’s policy choices. Risk factors at each level are identified alongside their causal mechanisms and, crucially, their interactions with factors at other levels, because the central argument of this paper is that isolated risks matter less than the compounding patterns that emerge when they converge.

The approach is qualitative and structured rather than probabilistic. It carries acknowledged limitations – availability bias in source selection, dependence on open-source reporting where classified or insider information would sharpen the picture, the absence of formal weighting that a quantitative risk model would require – yet its value lies not in

prediction but in the systematic exploration of failure pathways whose very identification can inform policy adjustment, a rationale that Mandel (2015) defends at length. The two analytical tools deployed here are therefore complementary in a precise sense: the pre-mortem maps *what* could go wrong across multiple levels, while the neoclassical realist framework explains *why* Turkey’s response to those risks is likely to be biased toward escalation rather than timely adjustment – a bias whose domestic sources Section 5.4 traces in detail.

4 Turkey’s composite engagement in Somalia: an overview

What distinguishes Turkey’s involvement in Somalia from conventional donor relationships is its deliberate entanglement of dimensions that other external actors tend to keep separate. Since Erdoğan’s landmark visit to Mogadishu in 2011, Ankara has built a presence that weaves humanitarian assistance into military cooperation, economic penetration into diplomatic mediation, such that pulling on any single thread risks unravelling the others. This is not accidental; it reflects what Donelli (2021) has characterised as a *composite strategy*, a mode of engagement in which the boundaries between aid, security, commerce and diplomacy are deliberately blurred to create an interdependent relationship that is harder for competitors to replicate and harder for the host state to exit.

4.1 Humanitarian and development aid

The humanitarian pillar was born in crisis. The 2011 famine killed an estimated 260,000 Somalis and Erdoğan’s decision to visit Mogadishu at the height of the catastrophe – accompanied by his family, in a gesture calculated to signal personal commitment rather than institutional routine – triggered a fundraising wave that channelled over \$370 million through state agencies and Islamic NGOs by 2016 alone, with cumulative assistance surpassing \$1 billion by 2021 (Aydın, 2020).³ What made this aid distinctive was less its scale than its architecture: Ankara operated bilaterally where Western donors worked through multilateral channels, emphasised direct implementation with Turkish personnel on the ground and conspicuously refused to condition assistance on governance reforms – a contrast with European development cooperation that resonated powerfully with Somali interlocutors accustomed to conditionality regimes (Sucuoglu and Stearns, 2016; Hackenesch, Leininger and Mross, 2020).

³Turkey’s overall development and humanitarian budget reached €8.8 billion in 2022 (0.79% of GNI), with Somalia the second-largest recipient after Syria at \$51.8 million in 2021. The share routed through multilateral organisations shrank from 3.6% in 2016 to 1.1% by 2021, reflecting Ankara’s systematic preference for bilateral channels (OECD, 2023).

4.2 Military presence and security cooperation

The military dimension grew incrementally before accelerating sharply. Camp Turksom, inaugurated in September 2017 at a cost of \$50 million, trained roughly 200 Somali soldiers per cohort under approximately 200 Turkish advisers; by 2020, approximately one in three Somali soldiers had received Turkish training (Rotondo, 2020; Ilhan and Demirci, 2020). The 2024 Defence and Economic Cooperation Framework Agreement transformed this conventional training mission into a full-spectrum commitment: within months of signing, a Turkish frigate docked at Mogadishu, a seismic survey vessel conducted an eight-month 3D survey of Somali waters under warship escort and parliament authorised the deployment of up to 2,500 troops.⁴ The trajectory is unmistakable: what began as advisory support has become a full-spectrum military commitment spanning land, sea and air, with sunk costs that are now material and contractual rather than merely reputational.

4.3 Economic investment, trade and the hydrocarbon dimension

The commercial relationship has grown alongside the military one, though its analytical significance lies less in aggregate trade figures – which rose from \$5.1 million in 2010 to \$384 million in 2024 with Turkish exports exceeding imports by a ratio of roughly 17:1 – than in the infrastructure of economic presence that underpins them: Turkish companies manage Mogadishu’s international airport and principal port, operate the only foreign bank in Somalia (Ziraat Katılım, established 2023) and have invested over \$100 million in FDI since 2018.⁵

The March 2024 hydrocarbon agreement adds a qualitatively different dimension. Granting Turkish Petroleum Corporation exploration rights over 15,000 km² under terms that have drawn pointed criticism – cost recovery provisions allowing up to 90% of annual production, royalties fixed at just 5% for Somalia and dispute jurisdiction assigned to Istanbul courts – the agreement risks transforming the political economy of the relationship from patronage to something closer to a concession regime.⁶ Whether this shift is already reshaping Somali perceptions of Turkey is a question the pre-mortem analysis addresses

⁴Subsequent deliveries have included three T-129 ATAK helicopters (June 2025) and three F-16 fighter jets (January 2026, with six more expected), extending the cooperation into the air domain for the first time. Turkish warships returned to Mogadishu in February 2026 for joint patrol coordination; the parliament renewed the deployment mandate in January 2026. The drilling vessel *Çağrı Bey* is expected in Somali waters for Turkey’s first deepwater exploration abroad. Sources: *Military Africa*, 23 April 2025; *Hüraan Online*, February 2026.

⁵Data from UN COMTRADE via TradingEconomics; TRT World Research Centre, *Turkey’s Economic Footprint in Somalia* (2023).

⁶“Turkey’s Somalia Oil Deal: Leaked Terms Spark Criticism,” *Nordic Monitor*, 22 April 2025; “Somali MPs Question Hydrocarbon Agreement with Turkey,” *Turkish Minute*, 3 July 2025.

directly.

4.4 Diplomatic mediation

The diplomatic thread runs through the entire period, though its character has shifted from reconciliation facilitation toward active crisis management. Turkey hosted Somali reconciliation conferences in Istanbul as early as 2012; the 2013 “Ankara Communiqué” sought to bridge the Somalia-Somaliland divide, although Somaliland subsequently questioned whether a state arming one party could credibly broker peace with the other – a tension that Cannon (2021) has analysed and that anticipates the “dual hat” dilemma discussed in Section 7. The most consequential intervention came on 11 December 2024, when Erdoğan mediated Ethiopia-Somalia trilateral talks that produced the “Ankara Declaration” – a genuine diplomatic achievement whose implementation has since stalled, exposing the structural fragility of Turkey’s simultaneous roles as Somalia’s military partner and the region’s honest broker.⁷

5 Pre-mortem analysis: vulnerability pathways for Turkey’s Somalia engagement

Applying the pre-mortem framework: *if Turkey’s composite engagement in Somalia fails within the medium term, the following factors – operating across local, regional and global levels – are the most plausible drivers of that failure.*

5.1 Local level: the fragility trap

5.1.1 Clan dynamics and the limits of state-building

Somalia’s political life remains structured around the “4.5 formula” – a power-sharing arrangement allocating equal representation to four major clans (Darod, Dir, Hawiye, Rahanweyn) and a half-share to a coalition of minority clans (Ahmed, 2019). Originally conceived as a transitional measure at the 2000 Arta Conference, this formula has become entrenched despite the 2012 Provisional Constitution’s intention to supersede it (Somali Dialogue Platform, 2023). Recent elections (2016, 2022) have maintained this clan-based indirect system, with only 14,025 clan delegates selecting the 275 members of the House of the People.

⁷The Declaration committed Ethiopia and Somalia to resolve tensions over the Somaliland MoU and envisaged technical negotiations concluding by June 2025. As of February 2026, no further formal rounds have been confirmed and the MoU remains unimplemented. See: “Accordo somalo-etiope per respingere le differenze,” *UNA-OIC*, 12 December 2024.

For Turkey’s engagement, clan fragmentation poses a structural dilemma: increased external resources intensify inter-clan competition for their distribution, potentially reinforcing the very fragmentation that state-building aims to overcome (Makinda, 1999; Menkhaus, 2018). Moreover, a fragmented political landscape facilitates the entry of competing external actors, each cultivating relationships with different clan factions. The hydrocarbon agreement’s extractive terms (Section 4.3) risk compounding this dynamic: the 90% cost recovery provision and the 5% royalty rate are politically vulnerable to reframing as a concession regime rather than a partnership – a reframing that Al-Shabaab and elite factions competing for resource rents have strong incentives to exploit. Should domestic perceptions of Turkey shift from development partner to concession-holder, the broad-based Somali popular support on which the composite strategy has relied since 2011 could erode independent of the security or regional factors analysed below, representing a vulnerability pathway autonomous from – but potentially compounding – those identified at the regional and global levels.

5.1.2 Al-Shabaab: a persistent and adaptive threat

Al-Shabaab remains, in the UN’s assessment, the “principal threat to the security of the region” (UNSC, 2023). The group has explicitly designated Turkey as an enemy since 2016 and has targeted Turkish development projects, military installations and civilian operations.⁸ While the 2022 Somali offensive achieved initial gains, Al-Shabaab has demonstrated a capacity for adaptation and resilience.⁹

The 2024 maritime defence agreement potentially increases Turkey’s exposure to Al-Shabaab operations, particularly against naval and port infrastructure.

5.1.3 Humanitarian “new normal” and climate shocks

As Dacrema (2022) has argued, humanitarian crises in Somalia can no longer be treated as “black swan” events but constitute a “new normal.” From 2020 to 2023 alone, flooding displaced 500,000 people, while over 8 million Somalis require humanitarian assistance (OCHA, 2023). The UN World Food Programme, which provides 80% of humanitarian assistance in Somalia, reported a funding shortfall of \$378 million in just five months (November 2022–April 2023).

⁸“Al-Shabaab Claims Attack on Turkish Military Base in Mogadishu,” *Reuters*, 30 September 2021.

⁹The 2022–2023 Somali offensive achieved initial gains in the centre-south of the country, but momentum stalled in 2024. Al-Shabaab retains control of vast rural areas and the capacity for asymmetric attacks in Mogadishu and other urban centres. For updated quantitative data on Al-Shabaab incidents, see the Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED), *Somalia Dataset (2024–2025)*; and the UN Panel of Experts on Somalia, reports to the Security Council (S/2024/..., S/2025/...).

For Turkey, the implications are clear: sustaining engagement in Somalia requires absorbing the costs of recurrent crises. With Turkey’s own economy under strain – inflation exceeding 60% in 2023-2024 and the lira at historic lows against the dollar – the fiscal sustainability of Ankara’s commitment is increasingly uncertain.¹⁰

5.2 Regional level: a crowded and volatile arena

5.2.1 The Ethiopia-Somaliland crisis and Turkey’s dual role

The Memorandum of Understanding signed between Ethiopia and Somaliland on 1 January 2024 – offering Addis Ababa access to a Red Sea port and potential naval base in exchange for possible recognition of Somaliland’s independence – triggered a major diplomatic crisis.¹¹

Turkey’s response has been to position itself as mediator, launching the ‘Ankara Process’ from July 2024 and hosting direct talks between President Mohamud and Prime Minister Abiy on 11–12 December 2024 – their first meeting in over a year. After seven hours of negotiations mediated by Erdoğan, the resulting ‘Ankara Declaration’ committed both parties to mutual recognition of territorial integrity (implicitly setting aside the Somaliland MoU), while acknowledging Ethiopia’s interest in sea access under Somali sovereignty. Technical negotiations were scheduled for February 2025 with completion by June. However, the fragility of the agreement was exposed within days when Ethiopian and Somali troops clashed at Doolow (Jubaland) and President Mohamud proceeded to visit Eritrea and Egypt – signalling that the anti-Ethiopian axis remains active. As of February 2026, the MoU is effectively frozen but no definitive resolution has been reached.

¹⁰Turkish annual inflation peaked at 85.4% in October 2022 and again at 65% in May 2024 (TUIK). The CBRT raised its policy rate to 50% in March 2024, then began cutting to 37% over the following year. Inflation declined to 30.65% in January 2026, but the lira continued its structural depreciation: from approximately 30 TRY/USD in early 2024 to 43.5 TRY/USD in January 2026 – a 21% loss against the dollar in 2025 alone. Turkey’s defence budget for 2025 exceeds \$45 billion and appears insulated from austerity measures, but the widening gap between military ambition and domestic purchasing power creates a political constraint on overseas commitments. Sources: TUIK; CBRT; ING Economic Forecast (January 2026); AGBI (December 2025).

¹¹The MoU was signed on 1 January 2024 between Prime Minister Abiy Ahmed and Somaliland President Muse Bihi Abdi. It reportedly offered Ethiopia a 20-km coastal strip near Berbera or Lughaya on a 50-year lease for use as a naval base, in exchange for formal recognition of Somaliland’s independence – which would make Ethiopia the first state to do so. Mogadiscio reacted by recalling its ambassador from Addis Ababa and securing diplomatic support from the Arab League, the AU (on the principle of territorial integrity), Turkey, Egypt, Eritrea and Djibouti. Somalia subsequently signed a defence pact with Egypt (August 2024). Turkey hosted Ethiopia-Somalia trilateral talks in Ankara on 11 December 2024. See: “Ethiopia-Somaliland deal: Why is it so controversial?,” *BBC News*, January 2024; International Crisis Group, *Averting a Crisis over Ethiopia’s Somaliland Deal* (2024). The December 2024 “Ankara Declaration” committed both parties to technical negotiations, but as of February 2026 the MoU remains unimplemented: Somalia considers it illegal, while Somaliland reiterates its commitment (Somaliland MFA, 2025). The impasse persists.

This mediating role sits uneasily alongside Turkey’s position as Somalia’s primary military partner – a tension that echoes the “dual hat” problem documented in UN peacekeeping and the structural incompatibility between armed partnership and mediation identified by Svensson (2007): a mediator who is simultaneously a party’s security guarantor cannot credibly commit to impartiality. Turkey simultaneously arms and trains Somali forces against threats that include Ethiopian interference, while claiming to be an honest broker between the two. The Doolow clash and Mohamud’s immediate post-Ankara visits to Eritrea and Egypt suggest that Somali actors themselves view Turkey’s mediation as complementary to, rather than a substitute for, the anti-Ethiopian axis. For Ethiopia, this undermines the credibility of the Ankara Process. The dual role represents a “triple diplomatic win” for Ankara in the short term (protecting investments, maintaining Ethiopian ties, consolidating broker status), but it may prove unsustainable: if the Ethiopia-Somaliland crisis escalates, Turkey will be forced to choose between its mediator identity and its alliance obligations – a choice that would damage whichever role it abandons.¹²

5.2.2 ATMIS/AUSSOM transition and the security vacuum

The transition from ATMIS to its successor mission represents a critical juncture. AUSSOM, authorised by UN Security Council Resolution 2767 (2024), became operational on 1 January 2025 with approximately 12,626 authorised troops – a significant reduction from ATMIS’s peak strength.¹³

The potential withdrawal or reduction of African Union forces creates a security vacuum that could be exploited by Al-Shabaab or filled by competing external actors. For Turkey, this scenario presents a dilemma: stepping in to fill the vacuum would require a significant increase in military commitment and expenditure, while standing aside would

¹²On the structural incompatibility between armed partnership and mediation, see Svensson, I. (2007). “Bargaining, Bias and Peace Brokers: How Rebels Commit to Peace,” *Journal of Peace Research*, 44(2), pp. 177–194. For the specific Turkey-Somalia-Ethiopia triangle, see: “Turkey’s Triple Diplomatic Win in the Horn,” *African Arguments*, January 2025; AEI Critical Threats Project, *Horn of Africa Update* (2025); *Geopolitical Monitor*, “Turkey’s Balancing Act Between Somalia and Ethiopia” (2025).

¹³Troop contributions were finalised on 25 February 2025: Uganda (4,500), Ethiopia (2,500 – readmitted after initial exclusion, following the Ankara Declaration), Djibouti (1,520), Kenya (1,410) and Egypt (1,091 – a first-ever deployment). Resolution 2809 (December 2025) reduced authorised strength to 11,826 for the period through December 2026. The mission faces a structural funding crisis: the intended hybrid model (75% UN assessed contributions via Resolution 2719/2023, 25% AU and donors) has not materialised, as the Security Council – primarily due to US opposition – failed to confirm assessed contributions by the May 2025 deadline. As of September 2025, confirmed funding covers only a fraction of the \$166.5 million annual budget: the AU Peace Fund pledged \$20 million (12%), the UK £16.5 million and Japan/South Korea \$4.5 million combined, leaving a significant gap. The EUISS (April 2025) has warned that the multilateral financing model risks ‘prolonged stagnation.’ Sources: UNSC Res. 2767 (2024), Res. 2809 (2025); EUISS (April 2025); UK Government (September 2025); DIIS; Security Council Report (May 2025).

risk losing the strategic position built over a decade.

5.2.3 Gulf rivalries and the Qatar factor

Turkey’s position in Somalia is structurally linked to its alliance with Qatar, which provides critical financial support for Ankara’s overseas operations (Maziad, 2018). The broader Gulf rivalry – with the UAE and Saudi Arabia supporting different factions within Somalia and cultivating relationships with Somaliland and federal member states – adds a layer of external competition that Turkey must navigate.

The 2024 maritime agreement intensifies this dynamic: Turkey’s acquisition of economic stakes in Somali maritime resources directly competes with UAE interests in the region, particularly Abu Dhabi’s investments in the port of Berbera (Somaliland) and its broader Red Sea strategy.

5.2.4 Houthi disruption and the Red Sea security complex

The Houthi attacks on commercial shipping in the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden since late 2023 have fundamentally altered the maritime security landscape of the region.¹⁴

Paradoxically, the Houthi crisis both justifies and complicates Turkey’s maritime engagement. It justifies the 2024 agreement by demonstrating the need for naval security in Somali waters. But it also attracts other naval powers to the region (US, EU, China, India), potentially reducing the power vacuum that Turkey had exploited, while simultaneously raising the risks and costs of maritime operations.

5.3 Global level: shifting tectonic plates

5.3.1 US retrenchment and the second Trump administration

The return of Donald Trump to the US presidency in January 2025 introduces significant uncertainty for the Horn of Africa. During his first term, Trump ordered the withdrawal

¹⁴Since November 2023, Houthi forces (Ansar Allah) have conducted systematic attacks on commercial shipping in the southern Red Sea, the Strait of Bab el-Mandeb and the Gulf of Aden, striking 99 vessels by September 2025 (Lloyd’s List). The impact has been devastating: container shipping via the Red Sea fell by 90% between December 2023 and February 2024 (US DIA); Suez Canal transits dropped from 2,068 (November 2023) to 877 (October 2024); oil flows through Bab el-Mandeb declined 55%, from 8.8 to 4 million barrels per day (US EIA). Major shipping lines diverted routes around the Cape of Good Hope, adding 11,000 nautical miles, 10 days and approximately \$1 million in fuel per voyage. Total disrupted trade value is estimated at \$1 trillion (October 2023–May 2024, Russell Group). Although the Houthis suspended attacks in November 2025 following a Gaza ceasefire, container traffic through Suez remained 86% below 2023 levels in Q4 2025 (BIMCO via gCaptain). Notably, the crisis has triggered a resurgence of Somali piracy: more attacks occurred in the first three months of 2024 than in all of 2023 (IMB), with reports of growing Houthi–Al-Shabaab collaboration (Africa Center for Strategic Studies). Turkey did not participate in either Operation Prosperity Guardian (US-UK) or EU ASPIDES. Sources: IMF PortWatch; Lloyd’s List Intelligence; UNCTAD; gCaptain (January 2026).

of approximately 700 special operations troops from Somalia in December 2020; President Biden redeployed approximately 450 troops in May 2022, restoring a permanent US presence for counter-terrorism operations and training of the Somali Danab special forces.¹⁵

US engagement in Somalia has been substantial: \$210 million in food assistance and \$430 million in humanitarian aid in 2023 alone, plus 61 tonnes of military equipment delivered to Mogadishu in the first three months of 2023.¹⁶ In mid-February 2024 – just days after the Turkish defence agreement – Mogadishu signed a separate \$100 million MoU with Washington for the construction of five new military bases and training of the Danab brigade. AFRICOM continues airstrikes against Al-Shabaab and ISIS-Somalia. The Trump administration has not significantly altered the operational approach, maintaining counter-terrorism cooperation. However, a reduction in US humanitarian and development funding – which USAID restructuring makes increasingly likely – would amplify the pressures on Turkey across all dimensions: militarily (increased security burden), financially (need to compensate for reduced humanitarian flows) and strategically (potential entry of competitors into the vacuum).

5.3.2 Great-power competition: the China factor

China’s Belt and Road Initiative has increased Beijing’s strategic interest in the Horn of Africa, exemplified by the establishment of a military base in Djibouti – 30 kilometres from Somaliland. While the US remains the dominant external power in the region, Washington’s strategic bandwidth is increasingly constrained by simultaneous commitments in Ukraine, the Middle East and the Indo-Pacific. A gradual American disengagement from the Horn of Africa, whether by design or distraction, would reshape the competitive landscape in which Turkey operates.

5.4 The domestic transmission belt: neoclassical realist variables and Turkey’s vulnerability

The preceding analysis has identified risk factors across three levels. But the neoclassical realist framework adopted in this paper requires a further step: explaining how these

¹⁵The second Trump administration has adopted a general posture of reducing overseas military commitments and drastically cutting foreign aid budgets. USAID has undergone severe restructuring affecting programmes across the Horn of Africa. As of February 2026, no formal withdrawal order from Somalia has been issued – unlike in the first Trump term (December 2020), when Biden’s subsequent reversal (May 2022) restored approximately 450 troops (BBC, 2022). AFRICOM continues operations under budgetary pressure. See: Congressional Research Service, *U.S. Military Operations in Somalia* (updated reports); AFRICOM press briefings (2025).

¹⁶“L’impegno USA in Somalia,” *Africa Rivista*, 2022; “US Military Deliveries to Somalia,” *Africa Express*, 2023.

systemic pressures are filtered through domestic variables before they produce foreign policy outcomes. As Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell (2016, p. 33) argue, the international system provides the broad parameters for state behaviour, but the precise nature of the response depends on “the imperfect transmission belt that links systemic incentives to foreign policy decisions.” In the Turkish case, four intervening variables mediate between the systemic risks catalogued above and Ankara’s actual capacity to sustain its Somalia engagement.

5.4.1 Leader images: Erdoğan’s Somalia as personal project

In neoclassical realism, leader images refer to the foreign policy executive’s (FPE) perception of systemic threats and opportunities.¹⁷ Turkey’s Somalia engagement is perhaps the clearest example of leader-driven foreign policy in Ankara’s contemporary repertoire. Erdoğan’s 2011 visit to Mogadishu – a calculated gesture that combined humanitarian symbolism with geopolitical signalling – was reportedly a personal decision taken against the reservations of security officials who considered the trip too dangerous (Wasuge, 2016; Sucuoglu and Stearns, 2016). Since then, successive escalations of commitment (Camp Turksom in 2017, the 2024 defence agreement, the hydrocarbon deal) bear the imprint of presidential initiative.

This matters analytically because leader images function as an amplifier of commitment under conditions that would otherwise counsel restraint. A rational-actor model focused solely on material incentives would predict that Turkey, facing inflation above 30%, a depreciating currency and no immediate security threat from the Horn of Africa, would scale back overseas commitments. That the opposite has occurred – the 2024 agreement represents a dramatic escalation – can only be explained by the FPE’s perception that Somalia is a core component of Turkey’s identity as a rising power. Erdoğan’s framing of the relationship in civilisational terms (“Muslim solidarity,” “Ottoman heritage,” “Turkey as voice of the *ummah*”) transforms what might otherwise be a discretionary engagement into a reputational commitment whose abandonment would carry domestic political costs exceeding its material value.

The vulnerability this creates is precise: the personalisation of the Somalia file makes it resistant to cost-benefit recalculation. Sunk costs – not merely financial but reputational and ideological – generate what Taliaferro (2004) terms *risk-acceptant behaviour in the periphery*: the FPE is willing to escalate commitments to avoid the perceived political catastrophe of acknowledging failure.¹⁸ The danger is that this escalation logic operates

¹⁷Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell (2016, pp. 58–62) define the FPE as “the leader and the group of individuals who have the authority and ability to commit state resources abroad.” In Turkey’s hyper-presidential system since 2018, it is effectively coterminous with Erdoğan’s inner circle.

¹⁸While Taliaferro’s original framework addresses great-power intervention, the underlying mechanism

independently of and potentially against, the signals being sent by the domestic economy.

5.4.2 Strategic culture: neo-Ottomanism, Blue Homeland and the “central state” doctrine

Turkey’s strategic culture provides the ideational infrastructure for power projection in the Horn of Africa. Three overlapping doctrinal currents are relevant.

First, the Strategic Depth (*Stratejik Derinlik*) doctrine articulated by Davutoğlu (2001) positioned Turkey as a “central state” (*merkez ülke*) with legitimate interests spanning the former Ottoman space – including the Red Sea littoral and the Horn of Africa. While Davutoğlu’s influence waned after 2016, the conceptual apparatus survived: Turkey’s self-understanding as a state with responsibilities beyond its immediate neighbourhood was internalised by the AKP foreign policy establishment.

Second, the Blue Homeland (*Mavi Vatan*) doctrine, originally formulated for the Eastern Mediterranean, has been progressively extended to the Red Sea and Indian Ocean. The 2024 maritime defence agreement can be read as the operational expression of Blue Homeland logic applied to the Somali coastline: the claim that Turkish maritime interests extend wherever Turkish naval capacity can be projected.

Third, the humanitarian-Islamic narrative that frames Turkey’s engagement in Somalia as distinct from Western interventionism. Donelli (2021) has termed this the “Ankara Consensus” – a model of engagement that combines bilateral aid, religious solidarity and commercial penetration without the governance conditionality that characterises EU development cooperation. This narrative provides domestic legitimacy for overseas expenditure, but it also constrains policy flexibility: any retrenchment from Somalia risks being framed domestically as an abandonment of fellow Muslims.

The interaction between strategic culture and the current risk environment is double-edged. On one hand, these doctrines create a strategic rationale for engagement that survives changes in the material environment: even if the economic case weakens, the cultural and ideological case persists. On the other, they generate *over-commitment bias*: the inability to distinguish between vital interests (where escalation is justified) and peripheral ventures (where it is not). In the Somali case, the doctrinal apparatus treats engagement as if it were a vital interest, while the material stakes – until the 2024 hydrocarbon agreement – were those of a peripheral venture.

– the FPE’s tendency to escalate to avoid the reputational costs of withdrawal – applies *a fortiori* to middle powers, whose narrower fiscal and strategic margins amplify the stakes of perceived failure.

5.4.3 State-society relations: the sustainability constraint

The neoclassical realist framework identifies state-society relations as a critical variable determining a government's ability to extract resources for foreign policy. In Turkey's case, this variable is under increasing strain.

Turkish public opinion has generally supported the Somalia engagement, which benefited from the “rally around the flag” effect of Erdoğan's 2011 visit and the high visibility of Turkish aid operations. However, as the engagement shifts from humanitarian assistance to military deployment and commercial extraction, the domestic politics change. The parliamentary debate on renewing the Somalia deployment mandate in January 2026 revealed significant opposition criticism – not of the strategic rationale, but of the cost. CHP legislators questioned the open-ended nature of the delegation and the lack of transparency over expenditures.¹⁹ The opposition argument is structurally potent: at a time when the minimum wage increase (27% in 2026) falls below inflation, the fiscal and political sustainability of a \$45-billion defence budget – insulated from austerity – is contestable.

The critical mechanism is this: as Turkey's economic crisis deepens, the FPE's capacity to maintain overseas commitments depends on its ability to prevent the Somalia engagement from becoming a domestic political issue. The 2024 agreement's economic component (30% revenue share, hydrocarbon concessions) can be read as an attempt to pre-empt this challenge by transforming Somalia from a fiscal liability into a revenue source. But this transformation is contingent on extractive success – which in turn depends on security conditions in Somali waters, the pace of deepwater exploration and global oil prices. The circular logic is visible: economic sustainability requires security, which requires military expenditure, which strains economic sustainability.

5.4.4 Domestic institutions: parliamentary delegation and the accountability gap

The final intervening variable, domestic institutions, shapes the procedural constraints on foreign policy. Turkey's 2017 constitutional reform concentrated foreign policy authority in the presidency, reducing parliamentary oversight to periodic mandate renewals. The Somalia deployment authorisation, renewed in January 2026, grants the president “broad discretion over scope, duration and operational details” – language that opposition legislators criticised as an abdication of parliamentary control.

In neoclassical realist terms, weak institutional constraints on the FPE facilitate rapid

¹⁹See the parliamentary debate on the January 2026 mandate renewal, in which opposition parties criticised the breadth of presidential discretion over deployment scope and duration (*Nordic Monitor*, January 2026). On Turkish public opinion and foreign policy, cf. also “Somali MPs Question Hydrocarbon Agreement,” *Turkish Minute*, 3 July 2025.

commitment escalation (as the 2024 agreement demonstrates) but inhibit course correction. When the executive faces few domestic veto players, it can pursue ambitious strategies abroad, but the same institutional architecture makes it harder to signal retreat or adjust commitments when conditions deteriorate. The risk is that Turkey's Somalia engagement acquires an institutional momentum that outlasts the strategic logic that initiated it.

5.4.5 Synthesis: how domestic variables shape vulnerability

The four intervening variables operate together to produce a distinctive pattern of vulnerability. Leader images and strategic culture amplify commitment by framing the engagement as a test of national identity rather than a discretionary investment. State-society relations create a time-bound constraint: as the economic crisis deepens, public tolerance for overseas expenditure erodes, creating pressure to produce tangible returns (hence the hydrocarbon agreement). Domestic institutions facilitate escalation but impede adjustment, locking in commitments that may exceed available resources.

The critical interaction is between leader images and economic constraints. The FPE's perception that Somalia is a vital interest creates resistance to retrenchment, while the macroeconomic deterioration (inflation at 30.65% in January 2026, lira depreciation of 21% in 2025 alone) progressively narrows the fiscal space for sustaining military and humanitarian commitments. This is not a contradiction that will resolve itself: it is a structural tension that will shape Turkey's policy choices in Somalia for the duration of the current economic cycle.

Table 1: Interaction matrix: intervening variables and systemic risk factors

Systemic risk	Leader images	Strategic culture	State-society	Institutions	
Al-Shabaab resurgence	Amplifies: escalates to avoid “defeat” narrative	FPE to “Muslim solidarity” prevents withdrawal	Mitigates (initially): rally effect	Amplifies: weak oversight allows rapid escalation	
AUSSOM collapse	Amplifies: sees vacuum as opportunity	FPE as <i>merkez</i> logic vs. awareness	Ambiguous: <i>ülke</i> risk	Amplifies: fiscal burden strains economy	Amplifies: presidential authority enables expansion
Turkish economic crisis	Amplifies: leader resists retrenchment as weakness	Ambiguous: extractive partly compensates	Mitigates: position pressure may force rationalisation	Amplifies: weak accountability delays correction	
Ethiopia-Somaliland re-escalation	Ambiguous: mediator role serves prestige but dual hat unsustainable	Amplifies: <i>merkez</i> demands engagement on both sides	Mitigates: low domestic salience	Ambiguous: flexibility allows nimble mediation but risks inconsistency	

Note: Assessment by the author. Of the 16 cells, 9 indicate amplification, 4 are ambiguous and only 3 indicate clear mitigation – reflecting the structural bias toward over-commitment in Turkey’s hyper-presidential system.

6 Discussion: the power-vacuum paradox

The pre-mortem analysis conducted in Sections 5.1–5.4 identifies risk factors across three levels of analysis and traces how they are filtered through domestic intervening variables. The central finding can now be stated formally: the most critical vulnerability facing Turkey’s Somalia engagement is not any single risk factor, but the interaction between systemic pressures and a domestic transmission belt that is structurally biased toward escalation.

We term this the *power-vacuum paradox*: Turkey’s success in building influence in Somalia has been facilitated by vacuums – the absence of a functional Somali state, the decline of American attention, the fragmentation of multilateral security frameworks. But filling those vacuums creates dependencies that make disengagement increasingly costly, while the conditions for sustained success (Somali state consolidation, regional stability, economic recovery in Turkey) remain largely outside Ankara’s control. Each escalation of commitment – from the 2011 humanitarian intervention to the 2017 military base to the

2024 defence agreement – deepens the dependency and raises the cost of failure.

This paradox has been dramatically amplified by the developments of 2024–2026. The defence agreement, the hydrocarbon deal, the deployment of up to 2,500 troops, the delivery of attack helicopters and F-16 fighter jets and the parliamentary renewal of the mandate in January 2026 have collectively transformed Turkey’s presence from a “soft power laboratory” (Donelli, 2021) into a full-spectrum military-economic commitment. Turkey now has naval assets, ground troops, air platforms, energy exploration vessels and commercial interests simultaneously operating in Somali territory. The sunk costs are no longer primarily reputational: they are material, contractual and – with the 30% revenue-sharing clause and hydrocarbon concessions – financially binding over decades. Disengagement has become not merely politically costly but structurally difficult.

6.1 Interaction patterns: how risks compound

The risk factors identified in the pre-mortem do not operate in isolation. Three interaction patterns, each linking factors across two or more levels of analysis, deserve particular attention.

Interaction 1: The local–regional cascade. This pattern links local fragility (Al-Shabaab resilience, humanitarian crises, clan fragmentation) with regional security architecture (AUSSOM’s structural weakness). The causal chain operates as follows: a deterioration in Somalia’s internal security environment – triggered, for instance, by an Al-Shabaab territorial offensive during a climate-induced humanitarian crisis – would expose the limitations of AUSSOM, which is chronically underfunded and operationally constrained.²⁰ If AUSSOM proves unable to respond effectively, the resulting security vacuum places an impossible dilemma on Turkey: absorb the burden of substitute security provider (requiring a dramatic and fiscally unsustainable increase in military commitment) or accept a contraction of the security perimeter, potentially losing access to the very maritime resources that the 2024 agreement was designed to secure.

The cascade is amplified by the domestic transmission belt identified in Section 4.4. Leader images (Erdogan’s personal identification with the Somalia project) and strategic culture (the “Ankara Consensus” that frames engagement in civilisational terms) push toward escalation, while state-society relations (mounting economic discontent) and fiscal constraints pull toward restraint. The result is likely to be delayed adjustment: Turkey continues to escalate for longer than material conditions warrant, then faces a sharper correction when the mismatch becomes untenable.

Interaction 2: The regional–global squeeze. This pattern links regional competi-

²⁰EUISS (April 2025); on the structural dependence of AU peace operations on external funding, see Williams, P.D. (2017). *Fighting for Peace in Somalia*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

tion (Gulf rivalries, the Ethiopia-Somaliland impasse) with global shifts (US retrenchment, great-power competition). Its logic is that of a competitive squeeze: the simultaneous intensification of Gulf competition – particularly UAE assertiveness in the Red Sea corridor and Egyptian military engagement in Somalia via AUSSOM – and the reduction of American strategic attention to the Horn would leave Turkey as the primary but isolated external security guarantor of a fragile state.

The critical mechanism is the loss of implicit American backing. The United States, while not formally allied with Turkey in Somalia, has provided indirect strategic cover through its counter-terrorism operations, humanitarian funding and diplomatic engagement. A reduction in this engagement – whether through Trump administration USAID cuts, AFRICOM budget constraints or strategic distraction – would remove the tacit framework within which Turkey has operated and expose Ankara to direct competition with actors (UAE, Egypt) that have both the financial resources and the strategic motivation to challenge its position.²¹

Turkey’s mediator role in the Ethiopia-Somaliland crisis compounds the vulnerability. The Ankara Declaration of December 2024 was a diplomatic success, but its implementation depends on conditions that Turkey does not control: Ethiopian willingness to abandon the Somaliland MoU, Somali willingness to offer alternative sea access and Somaliland’s acquiescence. If the Declaration unravels – and the Doolow clashes of December 2024, Ethiopia’s continued ambiguity and Mohamud’s post-Ankara visits to Cairo and Asmara all suggest fragility – Turkey would be forced to choose between its roles as Somalia’s military partner and the region’s honest broker. This is the structural “dual hat” dilemma that the mediation literature identifies as inherently unstable (Svensson, 2007): a mediator with material stakes in the outcome faces a credibility deficit with the party it does not arm.

Interaction 3: The domestic–systemic disconnect. This pattern is the most immediate and the most dangerous. It links Turkey’s expanding external commitments with its contracting domestic economic capacity. The numbers are stark: inflation stood at 30.65% in January 2026; the lira lost 21% of its value against the dollar in 2025; the minimum wage increase for 2026 (27%) fell below inflation, squeezing purchasing power; and the Central Bank’s policy rate, while declining from its peak of 50%, remained at 37% – a level that constrains investment and growth.

The defence budget of over \$45 billion in 2025 appears insulated from austerity, but this insulation is itself a political choice that becomes harder to sustain as domestic economic conditions deteriorate. Turkey’s Somalia engagement requires not just military

²¹This draws on the logic of “security interdependence” between the Middle East and Horn of Africa Regional Security Complexes identified by Cannon and Donelli (2020, pp. 511–514).

expenditure but the sustained operation of multiple civilian agencies (TİKA, Kızılay, Diyanet, Turkish hospitals and schools), commercial operators (airport, port, bank) and exploration activities (*Oruç Reis*, *Çağrı Bey*). The total cost envelope is not publicly disclosed, but it is substantially larger than the military deployment alone.

The temporal dimension is critical. The 2024 agreement attempts to address this disconnect by transforming Somalia from a fiscal liability into a revenue source (30% of EEZ revenues, hydrocarbon concessions). But revenue extraction depends on security (to protect exploration vessels and maritime operations), which depends on military expenditure, which depends on economic capacity. This circular dependency is the structural expression of the power-vacuum paradox at the domestic level.

Table 2 summarises the risk factors identified in the pre-mortem (Sections 4.1–4.3) at the systemic level, while Table 1 above shows how these systemic risks are filtered through the domestic intervening variables analysed in Section 4.4.

Table 2: Synoptic table of risk factors

Level	Risk factor	Causal mechanism	Impact
Local	Clan fragmentation and 4.5 formula	Resource competition fragments governance; enables external penetration	Medium
Local	Al-Shabaab resilience	Persistent insurgency; targeting of Turkish assets	High
Local	Climate/humanitarian shocks	Recurring crises increase cost of engagement	Medium
Local	Hydrocarbon agreement terms	Extractive provisions (90% cost recovery, 5% royalties) enable “concession-holder” reframing; erodes Somali popular support independent of security dynamics	High
Regional	Ethiopia-Somaliland crisis	Threatens Somali territorial integrity; strains Turkey’s dual mediator/ally role	High
Regional	AUSSOM transition and funding crisis	Security vacuum if withdrawal mismanaged; chronic underfunding	High
Regional	Gulf rivalries (UAE, Saudi Arabia)	Competition for influence; alternative partnerships for Somali actors	Medium
Regional	Houthi disruption in Red Sea	Increases strategic importance but also operational risks and costs	Medium
Global	US retrenchment (Trump 2.0)	Reduced security and humanitarian support; power vacuum	High
Global	China’s increasing presence	Alternative patron for Somali actors; complicates Turkey’s position-	Medium

6.2 Failure scenarios

The interaction patterns described above generate three illustrative scenarios of failure. These are not predictions; they are structured explorations of how the identified vulnerabilities could combine to produce outcomes that fall short of Turkey’s strategic objectives. Each scenario assumes that the medium-term trajectory (5–10 years) of Turkey’s engagement is determined by the interaction of systemic pressures with domestic filtering variables.

Scenario A: The cascading security collapse. *Trigger:* A severe climate shock (drought followed by flooding, consistent with the pattern documented by OCHA since 2020) coincides with an Al-Shabaab territorial offensive in central-southern Somalia, exploiting AUSSOM’s reduced troop strength and funding gaps. *Mechanism:* The humanitarian crisis overwhelms civilian response capacity, forcing the displacement of populations toward urban centres. Al-Shabaab capitalises on the displacement to establish control over rural areas, including territory near exploration blocks covered by the hydrocarbon agreement. AUSSOM, facing its chronic funding shortfall, is unable to mount an effective counter-offensive. The Somali Federal Government requests Turkish military reinforcement. *Domestic filtering:* The FPE’s leader images (Somalia as personal legacy) and strategic culture (Ankara Consensus obligations) push toward responding. But the Turkish economy is in a recession or severe slowdown; the lira has depreciated further; the opposition is attacking foreign military expenditure. The institutional architecture allows the FPE to authorise reinforcement without parliamentary approval, but the deployment triggers a cost spiral: more troops require more logistics, more force protection, more humanitarian support. *Outcome:* Turkey finds itself in a mission creep dynamic, incrementally expanding its military footprint to protect sunk costs while the conditions for extractive returns (hydrocarbons, fisheries) deteriorate. The engagement becomes a net fiscal drain without a credible exit pathway – the very scenario that the pre-mortem was designed to anticipate.

Scenario B: The regional unravelling. *Trigger:* The Ankara Declaration fails to produce a definitive resolution. Ethiopia, under pressure from domestic nationalist politics, reactivates the Somaliland MoU or negotiates a bilateral arrangement with Somaliland that bypasses Mogadishu. *Mechanism:* Somalia terminates the Ankara Process and accuses Turkey of failing to protect its territorial integrity. The Egypt-Eritrea-Somalia axis is reinvigorated and Cairo offers to replace Turkish military cooperation with Egyptian alternatives – a credible offer given Egypt’s existing AUSSOM deployment and its strategic interest in containing both Ethiopian and Turkish influence. The UAE, which had reduced its engagement after 2024, re-enters the Somali arena by supporting federal member states (particularly Puntland) as counterweights to Mogadishu’s central govern-

ment. *Domestic filtering*: Turkey’s strategic culture (*merkez ülke*, honest broker identity) is directly challenged: the narrative of Turkey as a uniquely trusted mediator collapses. The FPE faces a choice between doubling down on the Somali partnership (which now carries anti-Ethiopian and anti-Egyptian valence) and attempting to preserve the mediator role (which requires distance from Mogadishu). Either choice entails reputational costs. *Outcome*: Turkey’s engagement survives but is strategically downgraded: from regional power broker to one of several competing external partners, with its economic concessions vulnerable to renegotiation by a Somali government that now has alternatives. The “triple diplomatic win” becomes a zero-sum competition.

Scenario C: The fiscal reckoning. *Trigger*: Turkey’s economic crisis intensifies. A balance-of-payments shock, a disorderly lira depreciation beyond 55 TRY/USD or a collapse in investor confidence forces the government into an IMF programme or severe austerity. *Mechanism*: Under fiscal emergency, the defence budget’s insulation from austerity becomes politically untenable. Overseas commitments are the first discretionary expenditure to face scrutiny. The 2024 agreement’s revenue-sharing provisions have not yet generated significant returns: deepwater exploration is still in the early phase and the 30% EEZ revenue share is a medium-term prospect dependent on enforcement capacity against illegal fishing – which itself requires naval patrols that cost money. *Domestic filtering*: State-society relations become the dominant variable: public opposition to overseas military expenditure becomes electorally significant. The institutional architecture, which facilitated rapid commitment, now impedes orderly withdrawal: the 10-year agreement has no publicly known exit clause and the hydrocarbon concessions extend over the exploration period. Turkey faces not just a political choice but a contractual entanglement. *Outcome*: Turkey undertakes a degraded engagement: maintaining formal treaty commitments and a skeletal military presence while reducing operational tempo, humanitarian assistance and new investment. This is the most probable scenario in the absence of major external shocks. It preserves the framework of engagement while hollowing out its substance – a pattern familiar from other middle-power overextensions.

6.3 Comparative perspective: middle-power overextension

The vulnerability patterns identified here are not unique to Turkey. A structured comparison with France’s experience in the Sahel (2013–2023) illuminates the structural dynamics at play and allows a sharper specification of the conditions under which the power-vacuum paradox operates.

France’s Sahel engagement, from *Opération Serval* (2013) through *Opération Barkhane* (2014–2022), shares several structural features with Turkey’s Somalia trajectory: an initial intervention justified by an acute security crisis and alliance obligations; progressive

mission expansion from a bounded objective – halting the jihadist advance in Mali – to an open-ended counter-insurgency spanning five countries; growing entanglement of military, economic and diplomatic interests that progressively raised the cost of exit; and eventual withdrawal under the combined pressure of local political opposition, military overstretch and domestic fatigue.²²

The critical parallel lies in the burden-sharing structure. Henke (2019) has demonstrated that states participating in multilateral military operations rely systematically on side-payment mechanisms – financial transfers, diplomatic concessions and security guarantees – to sustain allied contributions and distribute operational costs; where those mechanisms are absent, the burden accumulates on the lead state until it becomes unsustainable. France’s Sahel operations were precisely such a case: predicated on implicit burden-sharing through G5 Sahel, EUTM Mali and EUCAP frameworks, they lost their cost-distribution logic when those frameworks proved unable to absorb France’s escalating commitments, leaving Paris to bear the full burden until domestic political support collapsed. Turkey’s situation in Somalia is structurally more exposed: the 2024 agreement was negotiated bilaterally, outside any burden-sharing framework, and Turkey’s simultaneous ambivalence toward AUSSOM – neither contributing troops nor formally endorsing the mission’s expanded mandate – means it has neither the cost-distribution benefits of multilateralism nor the political legitimacy that multilateral authorisation would provide.

The over-commitment dynamic operated in both cases through the same domestic mechanism. France, like Turkey, functioned in a permissive strategic environment where domestic variables – presidential prestige, post-colonial strategic culture, the institutional autonomy of the military establishment documented by Chafer and Bat (2013) – drove escalation beyond what material incentives justified. The result in France was a decade-long commitment that consumed substantial resources without producing the strategic outcomes – stable governance, a reduced jihadist threat – that justified the original investment. When domestic political support eroded and local governments turned hostile following the coup cycles of 2021–2023, France confronted precisely the dilemma now latent in Turkey’s Somalia engagement: the choice between costly persistence and a withdrawal whose reputational damage would be proportionate to the depth of the preceding commitment.

The differences are analytically important and bear directly on how the power-vacuum paradox may resolve in the Turkish case. France was expelled from the Sahel by military coups that installed explicitly anti-French governments – a discontinuous external shock

²²France deployed approximately 5,100 troops across the G5 Sahel at the peak of Barkhane (2014–2022). Withdrawal: Mali (August 2022), Burkina Faso (February 2023), Niger (December 2023). The EU’s EUTM Mali and EUCAP Sahel Niger missions were simultaneously suspended in 2022–2023, illustrating how French disengagement cascaded into multilateral frameworks.

that forced rapid disengagement regardless of French preferences. Turkey’s position in Somalia is, for now, secured by a cooperative federal government whose electoral survival depends in part on the security umbrella and development resources that Turkish engagement provides. This structural difference means that the paradox is more likely to resolve through Scenario C – degraded engagement rather than expulsion – than through the abrupt collapse that terminated France’s Sahel presence.

Yet the difference should not be overstated. France had no colonial history in Mali and Niger that it needed to manage; it was expelled for what it had done since 2013, not for what it had done before 1960. Turkey, similarly, brings no colonial legacy to Somalia. But the hydrocarbon agreement’s extractive terms – 90% cost recovery, 5% royalties, Istanbul jurisdiction – create conditions in which a “neo-colonial” reframing of Turkey’s presence is politically available to domestic opponents and regional competitors alike. The absence of a colonial past provides no immunity against the political economy of extraction; it merely means that the reframing, if it occurs, will require a shorter historical memory than France’s opponents required in the Sahel.

The broader structural lesson is that middle powers lack the strategic depth – the fiscal reserves, diplomatic bandwidth and military surplus – to sustain full-spectrum engagements in fragile states over extended periods, a dynamic well-documented in the state-building literature (Paris, 2004). Great powers can absorb setbacks through institutional resilience and fiscal scale; middle powers operate with thinner margins. When the domestic economic base weakens, the gap between ambition and capacity becomes the defining vulnerability.

The middle-power literature offers a further refinement. Jordaan (2003) and Nolte (2010) distinguish between traditional middle powers – established states with consolidated domestic institutions and stable extractive capacity – and emerging middle powers whose regional ambitions outpace the structural consolidation of their economic base. Turkey belongs unambiguously to the latter category, and the distinction matters: emerging middle powers face a compounded version of the over-commitment dynamic because their domestic fiscal base is structurally more fragile, their international credibility harder-won and their room for orderly disengagement narrower. Öniş and Kutlay (2020), in their analysis of Turkey’s structural position within the global core–periphery divide, have argued that the AKP’s pattern of simultaneous foreign policy expansion across multiple theatres reflects a political economy logic in which external activism serves to compensate for domestic structural vulnerabilities rather than to express them – a dynamic in which the appearance of strength conceals the underlying fragility of an emerging economy caught between developmental ambition and structural peripherality. The Somalia engagement, launched in 2011 at the peak of AKP domestic confidence but against the

background of Eurozone contagion risk and domestic credit expansion, exemplifies this logic precisely. The power-vacuum paradox, in this reading, is not an idiosyncratic feature of Turkey's Somalia policy but a structural tendency of emerging middle-power projection in fragile states.

6.4 The paradox formalised

The analysis can now be stated as a formal proposition within the neoclassical realist framework:

When a middle power projects composite power into a fragile state under permissive systemic conditions and when its domestic transmission belt is characterised by strong leader images, expansive strategic culture, weak institutional constraints and deteriorating extractive capacity, the resulting engagement trajectory tends toward over-commitment: each increment of investment raises the cost of withdrawal more than it raises the probability of success. The engagement becomes self-reinforcing but not self-sustaining – dependent on external conditions that the projecting state does not control.

Four scope conditions delimit the paradox's domain of application. First, the projecting state must be a middle power with structurally constrained extractive capacity – one for which the fiscal cost of overseas commitment is not absorbed as routine expenditure but competes with domestic political priorities. Second, the systemic environment must be permissive rather than compelling: where existential threats drive engagement, domestic variables have less scope to distort the cost-benefit calculation, and over-commitment is less likely because the corrective signal of strategic necessity is continuous and unambiguous. Third, the domestic transmission belt must be systematically biased toward escalation – a condition produced by the specific combination of strong leader images, expansive strategic culture, weak institutional constraints and deteriorating extractive capacity that Section 5.4 documents for Turkey. Fourth, the engagement must be in a fragile state where the conditions of success – governance consolidation, security sector reform, economic reconstruction – lie substantially outside the projecting state's control. When all four conditions are jointly satisfied, the paradox operates; when any is absent, the dynamic is altered. A great power (condition one absent) or a state under existential threat (condition two absent) or one with strong institutional constraints on executive discretion (condition three absent) or one engaging a consolidated state (condition four absent) would face a different risk calculus, one in which the corrective mechanisms that the paradox identifies as structurally blocked would have greater traction.

Turkey’s Somalia engagement, from the 2011 humanitarian intervention to the 2024 defence agreement, is a paradigmatic case of this dynamic. The 2024 agreement, by adding contractual and economic dimensions to what was previously a largely discretionary engagement, has hardened the commitment structure: Turkey’s exposure is now locked in by treaty obligations, revenue-sharing clauses, hydrocarbon concessions and the physical presence of troops, naval assets and exploration vessels. The paradox is that each of these commitment-hardening measures was individually rational – responding to real systemic pressures and opportunities – but their cumulative effect is to narrow Ankara’s room for manoeuvre at precisely the moment when flexibility is most needed.

This finding qualifies the largely positive assessments in the existing literature. Donelli (2021) and Cannon (2016) have documented Turkey’s innovative engagement model; Van den Berg and Meester (2019) have situated it within the “Ankara Consensus.” This paper does not dispute the achievements of that model, but argues that the 2024 agreement represents a qualitative shift that changes the risk calculus fundamentally. Turkey is no longer a humanitarian donor that can modulate its presence according to domestic circumstances. It is a treaty-bound military-economic partner with material interests, contractual obligations and sunk costs that constrain its future choices. The power-vacuum paradox suggests that the trajectory ahead is one of deepening entanglement rather than strategic optimisation – with the ultimate outcome depending less on Ankara’s choices than on the alignment of conditions it cannot control.

7 Conclusions: theoretical implications and policy relevance

The February 2024 Defence and Economic Cooperation Framework Agreement between Turkey and Somalia is not the culmination of a decade of Turkish engagement but its qualitative transformation. Where the preceding phase was characterised by a largely discretionary composite strategy – one that could be modulated, redirected or scaled back according to domestic political and economic conditions – the 2024 agreement hardened the commitment structure in ways that make ordered disengagement structurally difficult: treaty obligations bind for ten years, hydrocarbon concessions extend over the exploration period, revenue-sharing clauses presuppose sustained military enforcement capacity, and the physical presence of troops, naval assets and exploration vessels generates sunk costs that are material rather than merely reputational. Turkey is no longer a humanitarian donor that can exit gracefully; it is a treaty-bound military-economic partner whose options are constrained by the very commitments that define its strategic position.

7.1 Theoretical implications

The analysis presented here carries three implications for the theoretical literature.

First, the power-vacuum paradox contributes to the neoclassical realist literature by specifying a mechanism through which the domestic transmission belt generates systematically suboptimal outcomes in a particular class of cases. Ripsman, Taliaferro and Lobell (2016) demonstrate that domestic variables mediate between systemic signals and foreign policy outputs, but the direction of that mediation is treated as empirically variable – the transmission belt may amplify or dampen the impulse toward action. The power-vacuum paradox identifies a specific configuration – strong leader images combined with expansive strategic culture, weak institutional constraints and deteriorating extractive capacity – in which the transmission belt is structurally biased toward escalation. The implication for Type II permissive environments, where no compelling systemic threat disciplines policy, is that the corrective signal that would otherwise arrest over-commitment is absent. The paradox thus suggests a theoretical refinement: permissive environments are not merely permissive – they are actively dangerous for states whose domestic transmission belts amplify rather than constrain the escalatory impulse, because the usual feedback mechanism (mounting strategic cost) is experienced only after commitment has exceeded the state’s capacity to sustain it.

Second, the paper contributes to the middle-power literature by specifying the compounding vulnerability that distinguishes emerging middle powers from traditional ones. Jordaan (2003) and Nolte (2010) established the conceptual distinction; what remained underspecified was the mechanism through which that distinction translates into differential vulnerability to over-commitment. The argument advanced here is that emerging middle powers – those whose regional ambitions structurally precede the consolidation of their economic base – face a double bind in fragile-state engagements: their relative exclusion from great-power coordinating mechanisms means they absorb the full cost of security provision without the burden-sharing that multilateral frameworks would provide, while their structurally fragile extractive capacity means they cannot absorb sustained costs the way established middle powers (Australia, Canada, South Korea) or great powers can. The power-vacuum paradox is, in this sense, a structural tendency rather than a Turkish idiosyncrasy.

Third, the comparison with France in the Sahel suggests that the paradox may have applicability beyond the cases considered here. A clarification is necessary before proceeding: the four scope conditions identified in Section 6.4 derive from the neoclassical realist framework rather than from the Turkish case alone, and their specification precedes the comparative analysis rather than being constructed to fit it. That they are jointly satisfied in a structurally distinct case – a former colonial power operating through multilateral

frameworks rather than bilateral ones, in a geographically and culturally remote theatre – suggests that the paradox captures a general dynamic of middle-power engagement in fragile states rather than a Turkish idiosyncrasy or a post hoc rationalisation of the French experience. France’s Barkhane engagement shared all four conditions: France was acting as a middle power under fiscal constraint, in a permissive strategic environment (no direct threat to metropolitan territory), with a domestic transmission belt biased toward escalation (presidential prestige, post-colonial strategic culture, military institutional autonomy documented by Chafer and Bat, 2013) in a fragile multi-state environment where the conditions of success were largely outside French control. The outcome followed the paradox’s logic precisely: each incremental commitment raised the cost of withdrawal more than it raised the probability of success, until the engagement collapsed not through strategic choice but through the external shock of anti-French military coups. The Turkish case differs in one significant respect – no comparable expulsion mechanism is currently operative – but the underlying structural dynamic is identical.

7.2 Limitations

The analysis relies on open-source information and applies a qualitative rather than probabilistic methodology; the impact assessments in Table 2 are indicative rather than calibrated, and a more rigorous approach would require structured expert elicitation or probabilistic modelling beyond the scope of this paper. These limitations are inherent to the pre-mortem technique and are acknowledged rather than concealed.

7.3 Policy implications

Three policy implications follow, addressed to distinct audiences.

For Turkey: the sustainability of the Somalia engagement depends critically on economic recovery at home. The circular dependency identified in Section 6.1 – revenue extraction requires security, which requires military expenditure, which requires economic capacity – will not be broken by deepening commitments abroad but only by restoring the domestic fiscal base. Scenario C (the fiscal reckoning) suggests that the most effective “Somalia policy” Ankara can pursue in the short term is stabilising its own macroeconomic environment.

For regional actors: the Ethiopia-Somaliland crisis, Houthi disruption and AUSSOM’s structural funding crisis have created conditions in which uncoordinated external competition could destabilise the fragile gains achieved in Somalia. The chronic underfunding of AUSSOM – with only 12% of its annual budget covered by the AU Peace Fund as of September 2025 – is the most immediate empirical confirmation of the power-vacuum

paradox: if AUSSOM collapses, the alternatives are fragmented bilateral arrangements or accommodation with Al-Shabaab. The March 2023 joint statement (UAE, Qatar, Somalia, Turkey, UK, US) provides a model for coordinated engagement that should be deepened.

For European actors: Scenario C – the most probable trajectory – suggests that European actors should prepare for a period of degraded Turkish engagement rather than outright withdrawal. The EU’s experience with EUTM Somalia and its role as AMISOM/ATMIS’s largest funder positions it as a potential bridge between competing external actors. Italy, with its historical ties to Somalia and its command of EUTM Somalia since 2014, is particularly well-placed to mediate between Turkish unilateralism and multilateral frameworks – a role whose urgency increases as the power-vacuum paradox progressively narrows Ankara’s room for manoeuvre.²³

²³Turkey’s engagement in the Horn of Africa is best understood as part of a strategic continuum extending from the Eastern Mediterranean through the Red Sea to the Indian Ocean – a space in which European and Turkish interests intersect without being coordinated. The under-institutionalisation of this coordination is itself a vulnerability that the power-vacuum paradox makes more consequential: as Turkish capacity is constrained by domestic economic pressures, the absence of a multilateral framework to absorb the resulting gap leaves the field to actors (UAE, Egypt, China) whose strategic interests diverge more sharply from European ones.

References

- Ahmed, N.M. (2019). “Somalia’s Struggle to Integrate Traditional and Modern Governance Systems: The 4.5 Formula and the 2012 Provisional Constitution,” *Journal of Somali Studies*, 6(1), pp. 1–21.
- Aydın, A. (2020). “Turkey’s Foreign Aid to Somalia: Shifting Paradigms of International Development Cooperation,” in *Turkey’s Humanitarian Diplomacy*. Istanbul: Istanbul Policy Center.
- Chafer, T. and Bat, J. (eds.) (2013). *Francafrique: le Ruban Ombilical*. Bruxelles: GRIP. [See esp. Chapter 3, on the institutional autonomy of the French military establishment in sub-Saharan Africa.]
- Cannon, B.J. (2016). “Deconstructing Turkey’s Efforts in Somalia,” *Bildhaan: An International Journal of Somali Studies*, 16, pp. 14–29.
- Cannon, B.J. (2021). “Contextualizing Turkey’s Actions in Somalia: Insights from Somaliland,” *Bildhaan*, 21(13), pp. 118–139.
- Cannon, B.J. and Donelli, F. (2020). “Asymmetric Alliances and High Polarity: Evaluating Regional Security Complexes in the Horn of Africa,” *Third World Quarterly*, 41(3), pp. 505–524.
- Comiskey, J. and Larrañaga, M. (2019). *Climate Security: A Pre-Mortem Approach to a Sustainable Global Future*. Monterey: Center for Homeland Defense.
- Dacrema, E. (2022). “Shock climatici e crisi alimentari: il ‘New Normal’ che affama la Somalia,” *ISPI Commentary*, 7 October 2022.
- Davutoğlu, A. (2001). *Stratejik Derinlik: Türkiye’nin Uluslararası Konumu* [Strategic Depth: Turkey’s International Position]. Istanbul: Küre Yayınları.
- Donelli, F. (2021). *Turkey in Africa: Turkey’s Strategic Involvement in Sub-Saharan Africa*. London: I.B. Tauris/Bloomsbury.
- Henke, M.E. (2019). “Buying Allies: Payment Practices in Multilateral Military Coalition-Building,” *International Security*, 43(4), pp. 128–162.
- Hackenesch, C., Leininger, J. and Mross, K. (2020). “What the EU Should Do for Democracy Support in Africa,” *Discussion Paper No. 14*. Bonn: IDOS.
- Ilhan, E. and Demirci, A. (2020). “Turkey–Somalia Military Relations: A New Model for Security Cooperation in the Horn of Africa,” *Insight Turkey*, 22(1), pp. 187–206.
- International Crisis Group (2012). “Assessing Turkey’s Role in Somalia,” *Africa Briefing No. 92*. Brussels: ICG.

- International Crisis Group (2018). “Somalia and the Gulf Crisis,” *Africa Report* No. 260. Brussels: ICG.
- International Crisis Group (2024). *Averting a Crisis over Ethiopia’s Somaliland Deal*. Brussels: ICG.
- Jordaan, E. (2003). “The Concept of a Middle Power in International Relations: Distinguishing Between Emerging and Traditional Middle Powers,” *Politikon*, 30(2), pp. 165–181.
- Klein, G. (2007). “Performing a Project Premortem,” *Harvard Business Review*, 85(9), pp. 18–19.
- Makinda, S.M. (1999). “Clan Conflict and Factionalism in Somalia,” in *Warlords in International Relations*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mandel, D. (2015). “Accuracy of Intelligence Forecasts from the Intelligence Community Assessment Program,” *Intelligence and National Security*, 30(1).
- Maziad, M. (2018). “The Cost of the Turkey–Qatar Alliance and Hard Power Projection,” in *The Arab Gulf States and the West*. London: Routledge.
- Menkhaus, K. (2018). “Elite Bargains and Political Deals: Somalia Case Study,” *DFID Stabilisation Unit Guide*. London: FCDO.
- Nolte, D. (2010). “How to Compare Regional Powers: Analytical Concepts and Research Topics,” *Review of International Studies*, 36(4), pp. 881–901.
- OCHA (2023). *Humanitarian Needs Overview – Somalia: Humanitarian Programme Cycle 2023*. Geneva: OCHA.
- OECD (2023). “Türkiye,” in *Development Co-operation Profiles*. Paris: OECD.
- Öniş, Z. and Kutlay, M. (2020). “Reverse Transformation? Global Shifts, the Core–Periphery Divide and the Future of Turkish Political Economy,” *Development and Change*, 51(3), pp. 584–610.
- Ozkan, M. and Orakci, S. (2015). “Turkey as a ‘Political’ Actor in Africa,” *Journal of Eastern African Studies*, 9(2), pp. 343–357.
- Paris, R. (2004). *At War’s End: Building Peace After Civil Conflict*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Pherson, R.H. and Heuer, R.J. (2020). *Structured Analytic Techniques for Intelligence Analysis*, 3rd ed. Washington, DC: CQ Press.
- Ripsman, N.M., Taliaferro, J.W. and Lobell, S.E. (2016). *Neoclassical Realist Theory of International Politics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

- Rotondo, S. (2020). “Camp Turksom and Turkey’s Growing Military Footprint in the Horn of Africa,” *ISPI Analysis*, 12 March 2020.
- Somali Dialogue Platform (2023). *The Role of 4.5 in Democratization and Governance in Somalia*. Sudan: Rift Valley Institute.
- Sucuoglu, G. and Stearns, J. (2016). *Turkey in Somalia: Shifting Paradigms of Aid*. Johannesburg: SAIHA.
- Svensson, I. (2007). “Bargaining, Bias and Peace Brokers: How Rebels Commit to Peace,” *Journal of Peace Research*, 44(2), pp. 177–194.
- Taliaferro, J.W. (2004). *Balancing Risks: Great Power Intervention in the Periphery*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Uzun, E. (2021). “Neoclassical Realism and Turkish Foreign Policy: Domestic Sources of International Activism,” in A. Aydın-Düzgüt et al. (eds.), *The Routledge Handbook of Turkish Foreign Policy*. London: Routledge, pp. 89–103.
- UN (2013). *Famine in South-Central Somalia: Post-Hor Deyr Analysis*. Rome: FAO/FEWS NET.
- UNSC (2023). *Report of the Secretary-General on Somalia*, S/2023/443. New York: United Nations Security Council.
- Van den Berg, W. and Meester, J. (2019). “Turkey in the Horn of Africa: Between the Ankara Consensus and the Gulf Crisis,” *Clingendael*. The Hague.
- Vertin, Z. (2019). *Turkey and the New Scramble for Africa*. Washington, DC: Brookings Institution.
- Waltz, K.N. (1959). *Man, the State, and War: A Theoretical Analysis*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Wasuge, M. (2016). *Turkey’s Assistance Model in Somalia: Achieving Much with Little*. Mogadishu: Heritage Institute for Policy Studies.
- Williams, P.D. (2017). *Fighting for Peace in Somalia: A History and Analysis of the African Union Mission (AMISOM), 2007–2017*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Yaşar, N.T. (2022). *Unpacking Turkey’s Security Footprint in Africa: Trends and Implications for the EU*. Brussels: SWP.